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**Analysing the Efficacy of Repetitively Used
Normal Cockpit Checklists**

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**I certify that this project is wholly my own work and in
accordance with the project regulations.**

**All material that has been extracted from others has been
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Executive Summary

Normal cockpit checklists are crucial in aircraft operations by ensuring all necessary tasks have been completed as prescribed. Pilots perform them repetitively, mostly confirming their actions from a previous workflow. Despite fatal accidents in which the use of the correct checklist failed to detect a critical error, the associated cognitive effects, such as implicitly memorising and subsequently recalling checklist replies, have hardly been studied. Therefore, this study aims to assess whether natural cognitive processes restrict the efficacy of repetitively used cockpit checklists. The research methods consisted of descriptive research to measure the flight crews' detection rate of a technical error using the relevant checklist and an experiment to probe whether randomised checklist items affect the error detection rate compared to repetitively used normal checklists with a well-known sequence. The assumption was that a randomised checklist item sequence could prevent certain cognitive processes, resulting in a better error detection rate. Pilots were observed in a flight simulator to determine whether they detected a technical error using the appropriate checklist. The research findings revealed that 26% of these flight crews did not detect the error. The effect of human cognitive processes could not be tested due to insufficient observations, resulting in a sample size that was too small to be significant.

These findings suggest that normal cockpit checklists may not be efficacious enough in detecting incorrect conditions to a level of safety expected in commercial aviation. Correctly performed workflows mostly conceal this issue. It is essential to make pilots aware of the inherent danger of subconsciously responding to checklists from memory. Further research is recommended on the effects of cognitive processes on normal cockpit checklist execution.

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List of Abbreviations

App	Application Software or Mobile Application
ERCS	European Risk Classification Scheme
EFB	Electronic Flight Bag
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organization
NTSB	National Transportation Safety Board

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

In 1935, the United States Army Air Corps issued a new long-range bomber aircraft tender, and the Boeing 299 was about to win this competition. It was superior to the other two contestants but more complicated to operate. When a flight crew on a test flight missed removing a flight control lock and crashed after take-off, resulting in two fatalities, a different model with less complexity was selected. However, Boeing further tested the aircraft and invented the pilot's checklist to assist flight crews in completing all required steps. This intervention was successful as the initial test models continued flying without incidents, and more than ten thousand aircraft were ordered retrospectively. In World War II, this aircraft became known as the famous B-17, "the flying fortress" (Gawande, 2010).

Thenceforth, checklists have been a typical tool in aviation and were increasingly being used in other domains as well, whenever procedures or machinery became too complex to be reliably operated from memory. This includes other high-risk areas, such as healthcare or the nuclear power industry, as well as standard product manufacturing (Swain and Guttman, 1983; Hales and Pronovost, 2006). However, checklists hardly evolved until several aircraft accidents in the late 1980s made investigators aware of latent issues. Degani & Wiener (1991) became the first to scrutinise the function, format and design of checklists in their ground-breaking report *Human Factors of Flight-Deck Checklists: The Normal Checklist*. Further studies, including guidance material, followed, and authorities published provisions on design and procedural use. However, the working principle has remained unchanged.

1.2 Problem Statement

But is there any reason to question how checklists are used and whether they are always effective? Studies have shown that pilots sometimes skip individual items or omit checklists altogether (Federal Aviation Administration, 1995; Turner, 2001; Dismukes and Berman, 2010). However, the focus of this study is on checklists that are completed in their entirety and at the correct time but where pilots recall responses from memory

rather than consciously verifying the current state (Federal Aviation Administration, 1995; Dismukes et al., 2007; Dismukes and Berman, 2010). This usually remains unnoticed when the typical checklist reply confirms the present setting. But what happens if something is non-standard? The author has experienced this regularly in his flying career: pilots provided the expected response, although the setting was different and clearly indicated. For example, many aircraft types have two configuration settings acceptable for take-off. Still, one is predominantly selected and the common reply to the relevant checklist item. It is not uncommon for pilots to respond with this typical setting, even if the other configuration was intentionally selected moments ago. The crew member often realises the wrong reply immediately and corrects it. Nevertheless, the most common answer seems to be subconsciously stored and automatically recalled. This inherits the danger of overlooking a critical discrepancy. Dismukes and Berman (2010, p. 21) underscore, '[p]erforming checklists from memory is a clear violation of formal procedures, but airlines may underestimate the factors that encourage pilots to do this'. If flight crews had a natural tendency to memorise and recall checklist replies, they would need to consciously suppress the associated cognitive processes to perform checklists as desired. It is uncertain how reliably this could be done, particularly when a person is subject to fatigue or stressors such as time pressure.

Therefore, this study aims to assess whether natural cognitive processes restrict the efficacy of repetitively used cockpit checklists, which would question their suitability for detecting hazardous conditions.

1.3 Objectives

The overall research aim of this project is to assess the efficacy of normal cockpit checklists in detecting undesired conditions considering human cognitive processes.

The research paper will thus develop the following research objectives:

- RO1 To measure flight crews' detection rate of a technical error using a normal cockpit checklist.
- RO2 To probe whether cognitive effects influence the error detection rate during checklist execution.

This study aims to contribute to flight safety and the human factors research stream by scrutinising the efficacy of routine challenge-and-response checklists in light of normal human cognitive behaviours. A new checklist presentation that may potentially mitigate these effects will be tested.

1.4 Structure

The paper is based on Biggam's (2021) proposed framework. The literature review focuses on checklist functions and variants in aviation. It outlines previous studies on human factor issues of checklists and cognitive functions related to repetitive tasks. The significance of aviation checklists is highlighted by presenting several aviation accidents. The following subchapter illustrates technical alternatives that are already available and potential future solutions. Chapter 3 presents a risk assessment of inefficient checklist use. A bow-tie diagram visualises the risk of flight crews providing checklist responses from memory and the significance of checklists in aircraft operations. This is followed by a description of the methodology chosen to address the research gap in the fourth chapter. The research strategies for each objective, descriptive research and an experiment, are justified, and the hypothesis is developed. The data collection tool, a flight simulator observation, and the data analysis approach are explained. The possible limitations of these methods are listed. The subsequent chapter presents the findings of the study, which are divided into three parts: a general description of the collected data, followed by an analysis of the data for each research objective. This research concludes with a summary of the findings and areas for further research that have emerged from this study.

2 Literature Review

The following literature review first introduces the basic functionality and different variants of cockpit checklists. Potential drawbacks are analysed by exploring particular studies about their design and use, followed by an identification of habitual human cognitive processes that could influence the correct execution of checklist procedures. A review of aircraft accidents in which relevant checklists were used but failed to detect undesired states scrutinises their efficacy. The chapter concludes with alternative options for checklist presentation that could potentially mitigate some of the identified issues.

2.1 Functionality and Variants of Normal Checklists

The Cambridge Dictionary (2023) generically defines a checklist as ‘a list of things that you must think about, or that you must remember to do’. This essentially coincides with the shorter description in the Merriam-Webster Dictionary (2023) of ‘a list of things to be checked or done’. Thus, a checklist specifies a number of items that need to be dealt with. This could also apply to a ticked-off shopping list, depending on the interpretation. Although this study focuses on procedural items, the working method is identical. The *Handbook of Human Reliability Analysis with Emphasis on Nuclear Power Plant Applications* describes a checklist accordingly as ‘a written procedure in which each item is to be checked off with a pencil or (sic!) other writing instrument as its status is verified’ (Swain and Guttman, 1983, p. J-4). In addition to the checking function, this description adds a documentation that each item was addressed. Other high-risk industries like health care employ checklists similarly, e.g. to prepare for surgery or to control medication (Gawande, 2010). However, it is not ascertainable that providing evidence of each step’s completion would be an inherent checklist characteristic. Accordingly, Degani and Wiener (1991, p. 7) stipulate in an aviation context, ‘[t]he major function of the checklist is to ensure that the crew will properly configure the plane for flight, and maintain this level of quality throughout the flight, and in every flight’. This fits the original intention of the United States Army as described in the introduction and highlights the importance of the desired result rather than how this is achieved.

The aviation industry uses two methods of executing checklists, as depicted in Table 1. ‘Do-lists’ are performed as ‘read-and-do’ and sometimes called accordingly (Barshi et al., 2016, p. 36). This means a checklist item is read, the required action is performed, and optionally, it is called out afterwards. Hence, older studies described this principle as ‘call-do-response’ (Degani and Wiener, 1991, p. 19) or ‘challenge-do-verify’ (Federal Aviation Administration, 1995, p. 32). This keeps all crew members in the loop and allows for a structured, step-by-step approach. It is used for procedures that are too complex to be remembered, only rarely executed, similar to another one or a combination of the aforementioned. Therefore, the item description could be detailed, including explanations or additional information. Examples include abnormal, emergency, or supplementary procedures, e.g. for de-icing.

In contrast, this study focuses on normal checklists, which describe frequently performed procedures as part of a regular process, such as daily operations during a flight, also known as normal operations. Assuming the procedure is well-known, the item’s description can be brief. A familiar workflow is performed by memory, possibly in any convenient sequence, and the checklist is then used to verify the correct and complete execution. This method is predominantly called ‘challenge-response’ (Degani and Wiener, 1991, p. 19; Barshi et al., 2016, p. 36), as every item is successively read, checked, and an appropriate response announced. The queried item’s status should match the designated checklist answer. A reaction should otherwise follow, e.g. a rectification or explanation of why the deviation is acceptable. Consequently, it is essential to meticulously check items while learning checklists by heart undermines its control function (Dismukes and Berman, 2010). In multi-crew cockpits, one pilot typically challenges an item, and the other responds with the checked condition. Such a verification corresponds to a control function to prevent human errors of omission or mistakes, possibly influenced by stress or fatigue (Hales and Pronovost, 2006). This is especially relevant in normal operations, as tasks cannot always be performed in the same sequence, or workflows could be interrupted.

	Read- and-Do Checklists	Challenge-Response Checklists
Preparation	None	Performing Workflow Actions from Memory
Extent	Description of Items and Actions	Items and Designated Status
Objective	Instruction	Verification
Application	Rare Extensive Procedures	Recurring Normal Procedures
Prompt	Reading of Action to be Performed	Reading of Challenged Item
Reaction	Performing Action as Described	Checking Item's Status
Response	Confirmation of Performed Action (Optional)	Announcing Item's Status

Table 1: Comparison of Two Types of Aviation Checklists (own Illustration)

For instance, when an aircraft taxis to a remote position for de-icing, the flaps¹ are kept retracted until the ice removal procedure is completed instead of the usual extension after starting the engine. Therefore, pilots must remember to perform this task until take-off, which requires so-called “prospective memory” (Dismukes, 2010). Cues and triggers are often used as reminders, e.g. placing notes in the field of vision. Nevertheless, the potential for distractions and disruptions of crew members is high, especially during preflight. Consequently, checklists are intended to ensure nothing is missed. However, their execution is also prone to be forgotten, either in its entirety or the resumption of an interrupted checklist (Loukopoulos et al., 2009). Notwithstanding the relevance of potentially forgetting to perform or complete a normal checklist, this issue is beyond the scope of this study.

There have been different ways of presenting normal checklists to pilots, but only today's most prevalent ones are listed hereafter. They all have the common feature of being usable independently of extensive and potentially unwieldy manuals. This reduces the risk of

¹ Flaps are movable aerodynamic devices mounted on the wing of an aircraft. During take-off and landing, the flaps are extended to increase wing area and therefore lift, allowing the aircraft to fly slower. They are retracted when the aircraft is flying fast enough to reduce drag.

being disregarded due to cumbersome retrieval or use (Federal Aviation Administration, 1995). The original and still most widespread version is a paper checklist, often laminated for better durability. Advantages are low costs and easy usability, e.g. in terms of where to stow or how to hold it. On the other hand, it is impossible to track the progress with a pointer except for a user's finger, which makes it prone to skipping items (Degani and Wiener, 1991). To provide a progress indication and prominently display items to be checked in flight, many aircraft feature relevant checklists with a mechanical sliding pointer on the aircraft's control column (cf. left side of Figure 1).

Digital copies of the paper checklist without additional functionality are increasingly available on electronic flight bags (EFB). Their advantage is that they do not require additional lighting at night and are even easier and cheaper to revise. However, these variants are just as prone to skipping items as their hardcopy counterparts. Therefore, Rantz and Van Houton (2011) found no evidence that digital versions are superior to paper checklists. Furthermore, EFBs are often firmly installed near the side windows, requiring the pilot to turn away from relevant indications (cf. right side of Figure 1).

Figure 1: Different Static Checklist Presentations (own graphic)

These three variants share a common disadvantage. If a pilot defers an item to address it later, i.e. because the status is not yet as intended, there is no memory function to remember it (Degani and Wiener, 1993). Possible solutions include an interactive checklist application on the EFB or an electronic checklist integrated into aircraft avionics, allowing the pilot to tick off accomplished items (Boorman, 2001). These systems are analysed in more detail in Chapter 2.5.

2.2 Studies on Human Factor Issues of Normal Checklists

This chapter will analyse studies which identified cohesive human factor issues.

Three checklist-related accidents at the end of the 1980s (two detailed in Chapter 2.4) prompted several studies on the use and design of checklists. Degani and Wiener (1991) were the first to analyse associated human factors and proposed sixteen guidelines mainly addressing design issues such as extent, item sequencing and standardisation. Independently, they concluded that paper checklists comprise latent risks arising from users' psychological behaviours, e.g. experience-based mental models, habituation and trade-offs when rushed. Pilots had been observed recalling checklist challenges and the desired responses from memory, grouping several items or omitting parts due to distraction. The perceived superfluity of the checklist was found to be one of the underlying cognitive problems. As the preceding workflow is predominantly completed correctly, the subsequent checklist typically confirms the flight crew's actions, diminishing the discerned importance of this verification step. The authors acknowledged the difficulty of these issues and stated that they did not have a solution. The only suggestion in this regard was to touch or point at an appropriate indication of a checklist item to focus the attention on the item being checked.

The study *The Use and Design of Flightcrew Checklists and Manuals* (Turner and Huntley, 1991) directly resulted from a National Transportation Safety Board's recommendation following one of the accidents (NTSB, 1988). It analysed nearly two hundred checklist-related reports within a five-year sample, operator documentation, and a pilot survey. In 43% of the reports, pilots did not use checklists or missed items, which was attributed to a lack of pilot compliance due to insufficient training and checklist design. Over half of the records mentioned interruptions during checklist use or overlaps with other operational tasks. The study revealed deficiencies regarding the description of crew coordination and highlighted the importance of training and explicit provisions regarding checklist use, but it did not address cognitive issues. The report focussed its recommendations on standards for checklist layout and presentation instead, e.g. in terms of content, structure, font or use of colours. The suggestion to research the benefits of

alternative checklist presentations, such as electronic displays or audible solutions, is addressed in Chapter 2.5.

Based on their study cited above, Degani and Wiener (1993) published a second paper titled *Cockpit Checklists: Concepts, Design, and Use*, which additionally analysed paper checklist use during cockpit observation flights and airline pilot interviews. In line with the findings described above, they observed frequent disruptions and non-standard techniques during checklist use to save time induced by production pressure. For instance, only the challenged pilot checked items, omitting mutual redundancy. The study additionally listed responses recalled from memory and normal checklists incorrectly performed as read-and-do, losing the redundancy of a previous workflow. Furthermore, pilots reported situations in which they had perceived an incorrect status as the usual setting and had responded accordingly. Despite these psychological issues, the authors' suggestions targeted almost exclusively checklist design matters. It was recommended to increase pilots' awareness of the negative influence of operational pressures on checklist performance, but the underlying cognitive processes were not considered.

Contemporaneous, Barshi and Healy (1993) conducted three psychological experiments to analyse the effects of automatic behaviours (“automaticity”) in light of the repetitive performance of invariable checklists. Subjects with no aviation experience had to proofread a set of arithmetic problems. In the first experiment, this set was repeatedly presented in the same order to one group and in a varied order to another. The proofreading times of the fixed-order group decreased significantly compared to a smaller decrease in the times of the subjects with the varying order set. This confirmed the development of automaticity when tasks can be performed quicker and with less effort, or even subconsciously. Automaticity is commonly associated with expertise, such as pilot training, which involves consistently performing the same procedures or repeating checklists. The second group had no recognisable patterns, carefully checking each calculation. This is called “controlled processing” (Shiffrin and Schneider, 1977). The second experiment was identical except for errors randomly introduced in some sets after the first half had passed without irregularities. Therefore, subjects had the chance to develop automaticity before the first errors were supposed to be detected. The results

clearly showed that subjects who examined the varied-order sets found substantially more errors than their counterparts with the repetitive order, demonstrating an increased risk of not detecting undesired conditions if automaticity has developed. This finding is alarming regarding checklist use, considering their function in helping pilots detect errors. The third experiment used only the fixed-order sets for three different groups but introduced an alerting condition just before the erroneous set for two groups. These alerts consisted of a varied-order set for one group and a set with new arithmetic problems for the other, both error-free. Either alert triggered a comparably increased detection rate of the error in the subsequent set compared to the third group without such stimulus. Linking these results with aviation checklists, the authors described the following dilemma:

‘[P]ilots are asked to do the impossible; they are asked to develop automatic-like performance while maintaining controlled processing. One way to make their job more feasible is to introduce some variation into the checklist procedure.’ (Barshi and Healy, 1993, p. 504)

The study concluded that the theory’s practical implications on aviation checklists should be studied with pilots. The authors implied their intention for additional research in this field, but it was not carried out (Barshi, 2023). Therefore, their study remains the only one questioning the efficacy of normal checklists.

Being the recipient of several NTSB recommendations regarding checklists, the Federal Aviation Administration (1995) published a report echoing some previous findings: distractions and interruptions can interfere with critical content stored in the working memory while concurrent tasks create goal conflicts often induced by production pressures. The importance of connecting the initiation of checklists with reliable trigger events was highlighted to avoid the risk of omission. Such cues could be actions like taxiing or commencing descent. However, the recommendations widely spared cognitive issues and concentrated on design aspects.

The Limits of Expertise - Rethinking Pilot Error and the Causes of Airline Accidents (Dismukes et al., 2007) analysed 19 aviation accidents. The authors determined automaticity and the risk of omission as hazardous factors for checklists. They also mentioned "expectation bias" when pilots must confirm an action they just performed in

the preceding workflow. This is particularly problematic considering “source memory confusion”, which is the confusion of two past events (Johnson et al., 1993). For instance, a pilot may believe that a particular checklist has already been read when, in reality, this recollection occurred during another flight, potentially on the same day. The proposed solutions focused mainly on the individuals’ responsibility, suggesting the pointing principle and invoking a disciplined, deliberately slowed-down checklist execution (Dismukes et al., 2007).

Loukopoulos et al. (2009) dedicated a whole book to the complexities and overlaps of simultaneous tasks in daily flight operations, describing goal conflicts involving checklist use as already outlined in several of the abovementioned studies. The authors analysed the resulting cognitive effects, such as the necessity for prospective memory when intentions are deferred, involving the risk of omission or the consequences of interleaving concurrent challenges, potentially resulting in substandard performance. These issues are naturally connected with checklists, often performed parallel to the aircraft operation. The authors thus assessed that typical checklists are prone to the same errors they are supposed to prevent, namely omissions and working mistakes. The issues listed aligned with Dismukes et al. (2007): automaticity, expectation bias and source memory confusion. The dilemma described by Barshi and Healy (1993) was confirmed, stating that expertise is associated with swift and effortless execution, not conveying the risks of automaticity. The suggested solutions were confined to self-discipline, training, crew resource management, and procedures allowing undisturbed checklist performance, e.g. moving checklist items to stationary phases of flight, such as before taxi.

A study published in 2010 analysing 60 cockpit observation flights identified 194 deviations in checklist use, 43 of which involved a pilot responding without a prior visual check of the indication or giving the expected but incorrect reply (Dismukes and Berman, 2010). Only six of these deviations were corrected. The authors named the factors already discussed above, suggested increasing flight crew’s awareness of their vulnerability to perform checklists automatically and highlighted the importance of a deliberate execution. A lack of studies scrutinising the checklist operating principle was determined, calling for empirical research. An alleviation of the risks was seen in modern integrated

electronic checklists, which can sense the states of many items and even alert the crew if a checklist was not completed at a given time (cf. Chapter 2.5).

In summary, most studies recognise the conflict between automaticity developed through constant repetition and the deliberate verification of checklist items, amplified by the typical working environment with goal conflicts and disruptions. However, only Barshi and Healy (1993) provided evidence of this effect, albeit without involving pilots. No further studies specifically addressed this issue or explored potential solutions. This indicates that the efficacy of normal cockpit checklists in detecting undesired conditions has not yet been scrutinised.

2.3 Brain Functions with Regards to Repetitive Tasks

Discussing human factors leads to considerations of cognitive processes. The human brain is faced with countless sensory information. It is impossible to process them all in parallel. Therefore, the brain has to prioritise and filter out certain inputs. Additionally, information is stored and retrieved when a similar situation is encountered instead of processing stimuli over and over again. This accelerates cognitive reactions and decreases the brain's workload, e.g. when identifying objects despite slightly divergent features or hearing familiar sounds as required in understanding speech (Anderson, 2009). This process occurs subconsciously, without any deliberate effort on the part of the individual. Persons may not even realise they are learning in such a situation (Eysenck and Keane, 2020). By intuitively building on repeated past experiences, so-called repetition priming is similar to explicit skill learning. Once experienced sufficiently often, even complex tasks can be performed without conscious perception (Poldrack and Gabrieli, 2001), e.g. typing quickly on a keyboard even though it has never been deliberately practised.

Therefore, operators may inadvertently memorise the correlation between a checklist and its corresponding responses, even though they should not. It is thus essential to consider what could trigger the retrieval of such memory during the checklist execution.

Our brains constantly search for known information, e.g. a set of letters forming a word. Such pattern recognition has mainly been studied in the visual context (Bartlett, 1998; Eysenck and Keane, 2020). However, the theory can also be applied to a broader context,

such as audible patterns in speech. Hearing a well-known sequence of checklist items and their assigned responses corresponds to such auditory priming (Church and Schacter, 1994; Moss et al., 1995). This could trigger memorised information, such as the next item on the checklist or a designated reply. While a single checklist item often has two (or more) states that could represent the correct response (e.g. the gear could be commanded up or down), there is typically only one expected response embedded in the item sequence of a particular checklist (e.g. the gear should always be down when reading the landing checklist). Such implicitly learned responses to recognised patterns are complex to alter or suppress and can prevent controlled processing (cf. Chapter 2.2; Shiffrin and Schneider, 1977). Pilots are expected to exhibit automaticity in most situations. This is considered expert behaviour (Barshi and Healy, 1993). However, during checklist execution, pilots must actively counteract natural cognitive reactions and deliberately check recurring items relying on their discipline and mindfulness (Dismukes et al., 2007). It is crucial to examine whether this can always be accomplished reliably.

There are additional cognitive processes which can interfere with this expectation. First, the challenge-and-response concept requires a preceding workflow to execute the tasks which are subsequently checked. Pilots expect the checklist to confirm what they just did and could perceive it as redundant. Additionally, there are no consequences for not checking the items meticulously if everything was set correctly (Dismukes et al., 2007). Relying on such a precondition has often been described as complacency. Parasuraman et al. (1993) found that humans are especially likely to become complacent when operating highly reliable automated systems. The repetitive execution of checklists that consistently confirm the correct outcome of a previous workflow can also be considered a reliable automated process. Complacency has often been cited in accident investigations to blame individuals. However, this cognitive behaviour can be explained with inductive reasoning (Girelli et al., 2004; Hayes and Heit, 2018). The brain constantly tries to predict future events based on past experiences. The more often a given situation repeats itself, the more likely we expect it to happen in the future. Without an individual's own negative experience or an appropriate alert, the importance of a disciplined checklist execution can easily be underestimated or forgotten (Degani and Wiener, 1991). Even worse, the brain could interpret information as expected instead of apprehending reality, e.g. when a pilot

looks at a display indication but conceives the value incorrectly. This is known as expectation bias. Dismukes and Berman (2010, p. 21) described this during their observation flights as ‘looking without seeing’. This issue is particularly pertinent when operators are subject to external stressors such as time pressure or distraction, which can result in the reversion to known patterns (Eysenck and Keane, 2020). These factors can significantly impair the ability to defy innate cognitive processes of pattern recognition despite best intentions. This raises questions about the impact on checklist execution.

2.4 Accidents Associated with Inefficacious Checklist Use

The previous chapters have analysed potential human factor issues connected with using normal checklists. However, it still needs to be proven that these can pose a risk to aviation. Several accidents have occurred already in which errors remained unnoticed despite the full completion of the correct checklist.

In November 1974, the leading edge flaps of a Lufthansa Boeing 747 operating flight LH540 did not extend before take-off from Nairobi due to a misconfigured pneumatic system. Neither the responsible flight engineer nor the pilots detected the discrepancy. The post-accident analysis of the cockpit voice recorder revealed that the commander stated the selected flap setting in reply to the checklist challenge. The take-off configuration warning system could not detect the error, as it did not monitor the leading edge flaps at that time. Consequently, the normal checklist represented the final line of defence, yet it proved inefficacious. With less lift than anticipated, the aircraft stalled just after departure and was destroyed by ground impact. Out of the 156 occupants, 59 lost their lives, and 54 were injured. The investigation report recommended, among others, to include the leading edge flaps in the take-off configuration warning system and to introduce cross-checks of critical items on the flight engineer’s panel by the captain. The incorrect checklist response was not queried (ICAO, 1976).

A similar sequence of events happened to Delta flight 1141 in Dallas in August 1988. The first officer was interrupted several times by non-standard conversations and other cockpit duties during taxi-out when it would have been expected to extend the slats and flaps. During a rushed line-up on the take-off runway, he responded to the challenged

checklist item “FLAPS” with the designated but incorrect setting. Neither the commander nor the second officer recognised the error. As the take-off warning system did not activate due to an intermittent failure, the aircraft took off but stalled immediately after lift-off. The aircraft was destroyed. 12 passengers and two crew members were killed, 76 people were injured, and only 18 passengers escaped unharmed. Due to the system failure, the checklist had become the sole control for this omission. The NTSB recommended, among others, that all flight crew members should be made responsible for checking critical checklist items. The accident report mentions the possibility that pilots could respond from memory with what they are used to saying due to the repetitive nature of the checklist. However, a possible solution was only identified in crew members’ self-discipline (NTSB, 1989).

In September 1989, USAir flight 5050 was scheduled to depart from New York’s LaGuardia airport. During the ground time of the Boeing 737, the rudder trim had moved to the full left position. The reason could not be determined. The pilots did not detect this during preflight preparations and taxi-out. When the first officer read the checklist item “stabilizer and trim”, the commander incorrectly replied with the usual response ‘set for takeoff’. During the subsequent take-off roll, the fully deflected rudder trim caused directional control problems, finally leading to a rejected take-off after the relevant decision speed. The aircraft overran the runway, resulting in its destruction. Two out of the 57 passengers lost their lives, and 21 occupants sustained injuries. The accident report did not include any recommendations on checklist use despite the failure of this decisive barrier (NTSB, 1990).

One of the best-known accidents in the aviation community was Helios Airways flight 522 in August 2005. Following a maintenance pressurisation test before the flight, the pressurisation mode selector of the Boeing 737 remained manual while the usual setting was the automatic mode. The pilots did not detect this discrepancy during preflight preparation. Two checklists required the flight crew to check the pressurisation system but the manual setting remained unnoticed. The 30-minute recording timeframe of the cockpit voice recorder did not cover the execution of these two checklists. Therefore, it is impossible to ascertain whether the flight crew responded incorrectly to the relevant

item or if the checklists had not been read at all. Due to the manual setting, the aircraft did not pressurise after take-off. The flight crew misinterpreted the aural cabin altitude warning with the take-off configuration warning, which had the same tone. The decreasing air pressure finally incapacitated both pilots. The aircraft continued along the programmed route until all fuel was consumed, and it crashed near its intended destination, Athen's airport. All 121 persons on board died. The investigation report mentions human factors like falsely verifying an expected result during accustomed activities and automatically performing checklists from memory, especially when under time pressure. It was recommended, among others, to enhance the preflight checklist's design concerning the pressurisation system, but the risk of incorrect checklist responses was not addressed (AAIASB, 2006).

In August 2008, a Spanair DC-9 operating flight 5022 had to return to its parking stand at Madrid airport to solve a technical issue. Running behind schedule, the commander pushed the first officer to depart quickly. When reading the "Before Start" checklist, the captain made several replies to checklist items which had not yet been challenged. The crew did not extend the slats and flaps after engine start. The corresponding item on the "After Start" checklist was missed as the checklist was prematurely interrupted to request taxi clearance. A conversation with a jump seat occupant prevented the required take-off briefing during taxi-out, which should have included a check of the flaps. The first officer stated the expected flap setting during the "Takeoff Imminent" checklist despite their fully retracted position. The commander did not monitor the checklist items during the simultaneous line-up on the runway. The take-off warning system malfunctioned and did not issue a configuration warning. The aircraft stalled and crashed seconds after take-off, killing 154 of the 172 occupants. The investigation report mentions expectation bias and perceiving things without looking during long and repeatedly exercised activities, which are even more likely under time pressure or a high workload. The captain's ability to cite checklist responses without being challenged is additionally highlighted. One recommendation was to compile industry best practices on checklist design, procedures, and working methods (CIAIAC, 2011). However, the risk of recalling checklist items from memory was not explicitly mentioned. This issue was also overlooked when Spain

presented opportunities to improve aircraft checklists on behalf of the European Union (ICAO, 2010). Despite subsequent recommendations to review checklist issues in the appropriate ICAO panel, the relevant documents have not been amended to date (ICAO, 2018; ICAO, 2022).

These accidents highlight the need to evaluate the efficacy of normal cockpit checklists in detecting undesired conditions and raise questions about the intended significance of checklists in aircraft operations. However, focusing solely on events with adverse outcomes presents a biased perspective as it does not provide information on situations when nothing undesirable occurred. Therefore, Chapter 3 includes a risk assessment to analyse this issue further.

2.5 Alternative Means of Presenting Normal Checklists Mitigating Human Factors

Static checklists have been in use for many decades. Although the content has been subject to studies and consequent improvement, the presentation remained the same for the longest time. The introduction of digital replicas, enabled by the increased availability of displays in modern cockpits, did not address the aforementioned human factor issues either. This chapter will analyse other checklist solutions that may mitigate some problems.

The most straightforward implementation is an interactive checklist application not connected to aircraft sensors, typically installed on an EFB. An example is Airbus' "Electronic QRH" application (cf. Figure 2). The crew member is supposed to tick off each checklist item as completed once the correct response has been given. This corresponds to the documentation function mentioned in Chapter 2.1 (Swain and Guttmann, 1983). The application monitors the progress and alerts the user if a subsequent checklist is selected before completing the previous one (NAVBLUE, 2020). The crew can quickly determine whether all elements or an entire checklist have been completed, allowing them to defer items if necessary (Palmer and Degani, 1991; Degani and Wiener, 1993). This feature should reduce the risk of omitting individual items or an entire checklist. Accordingly, Rouse and Rouse (1980) found that using interactive

checklists results in fewer errors than hardcopy versions. Boorman (2001) supports this finding but highlights the risk of inadvertently ticking off a wrong item.

Figure 2: Interactive Checklist Application (NAVBLUE, 2020)

However, this solution does not address the issue of responding to checklists as expected or memorised. If the display is located outside the field of view for the items to be checked, the challenging pilot may even be reluctant to check the items individually (Civil Aviation Authority, 2000). Nevertheless, these checklist presentations often replace paper checklists. They will likely be used until the end of the life cycle of aircraft generations that have entered into service with this standard.

Considering human weaknesses in repetitive monitoring tasks as outlined by Fitts (1951) with the HABA-MABA² approach, it seems only logical to cede the responsibility for checking to machines as far as practicable. This requires aircraft-integrated electronic checklists that sense switch positions, configuration settings, and values. The human operator typically selects the appropriate checklist or it is automatically displayed when certain trigger conditions are met (Boorman, 2001). The system will always display the correct status as long as the sensor data is available and correct. All items that match the intended setting are automatically displayed as completed, while all others stand out (cf.

² Humans Are Better At/Machines Are Better At

Figure 3). The Federal Aviation Administration (1996) calls this a ‘closed loop’ and acknowledges a reduced heads-down time. Only items the system cannot sense, e.g., whether the pilots performed a briefing, must be checked and ticked off by the user to complete the list.

Figure 3: Integrated Electronic Checklist with closed-loop function (own graphic)

Dismukes and Berman (2010) consequently assert a reduced vulnerability to checklist deviations, which they had recorded in their observation. Boorman (2001) equally determines that integrated electronic checklists can solve all normal checklist error modes listed in his study, including a pilot's recall of a memorised checklist reply. However, safeguarding from omitting entire checklists requires an alerting system to be activated if checklists have not been completed at a predetermined stage (Boorman, 2001; Dismukes and Berman, 2010). For instance, an alert would sound if the landing checklist was not completed before passing a certain height. This is hardly implemented today, but integrated electronic checklists without alerting features are increasingly available in new aircraft types entering into service. They could mitigate incorrect checklist responses from memory. However, it is essential to note that users may rely too heavily on automation. In the case of integrated electronic checklists, pilots may be less inclined to conduct individual checks (Palmer and Degani, 1991) and are typically not obliged to do

so by the manufacturer or airline procedures. Therefore, it is imperative that the electronic checklist consistently and reliably senses and displays all items (Mosier et al., 1992).

Another, but only scientific approach consists of using interventions that aim to improve checklist discipline (Hilton, 2012). In a single-pilot cockpit study, an audible checklist was used, which read items, awaited the pilot's response, and then continued with the next element. Once the checklist was completed and if items had been executed incorrectly, an indication prompted the pilot to restart the list. While this function was only simulated, its mechanism could be compared with a closed-loop checklist apart from the volunteers not knowing what they did wrong. Nevertheless, this feedback influenced the subjects, as Hilton (2012) could ascertain a substantially increased performance of all participants while using the intelligent audible checklist. This confirms the findings of two other studies where participants received direct feedback on their checklist performance, improving to near-perfect execution (Rantz et al., 2009; Rantz and van Houten, 2011). Finally, as suggested by Barshi and Healy (1993; cf. Chapter 2.2), alerting stimuli could also be considered an intervention and might have the same positive effect on checklist discipline. A feasible approach could be randomly displaying warning notes on an interactive checklist. It is important to note that the three aforementioned studies were conducted in a simulated environment and did not involve professional pilots. Therefore, it is uncertain whether the impact of interventions is equally applicable to checklist usage in a commercial multi-crew cockpit and whether the effect diminishes over time.

In summary, the safest approach to prevent negative consequences caused by human factors is to use integrated electronic checklists with closed-loop items. This is the only unequivocal barrier against incorrect checklist responses from memory. However, retrofit solutions are hardly viable. Due to the lifespan of aircraft, many flight crews may not have access to this tool for years.

2.6 Summary and Emerging Issues

The previous chapters reviewed the academic literature on checklist functionality, variants and human factors, focusing on human cognitive processes. Following a

preceding workflow, challenge-and-response normal checklists are intended to ensure that all required tasks have been completed satisfactorily achieving a desired state. The static checklist presentation on paper or an EFB is still the primary implementation on many aircraft types. The impact of cognitive effects on checklist execution, such as implicit learning of repetitive checklist replies, has received little attention. Barshi and Healy (1993) were the only ones to address the issue of automaticity and the recall of expected replies due to pattern recognition. During checklist execution, pilots must suppress automatic behaviour, which is otherwise expected. Interventions may induce controlled processing, but this has never been examined with commercial pilots. Past suggestions for further research scrutinising normal checklist operating principles have not been addressed despite fatal accidents in which the use of a static checklist failed to detect a critical error. One possible solution is to utilise aircraft-integrated electronic checklists with closed-loop item sensing. However, this technology is currently only available on new aircraft types, and retrofits are unlikely.

In conclusion, the literature review indicates that the efficacy of static aviation normal checklists in detecting undesired conditions has never been examined, nor has the impact of cognitive effects on normal cockpit checklist execution been thoroughly analysed. This study intends to address this research gap.

3 Risk Assessment for Inefficacious Checklist Execution

Chapter 2.4 provided examples of accidents that occurred despite the relevant checklist having been performed entirely and at the intended time. In all but one case, cockpit voice recordings were available, providing evidence that an intended setting had been confirmed, which could not have been indicated. Therefore, the checklists were inefficacious in detecting the incorrect condition. This raises questions about the risk of flight crews providing checklist responses from memory and the significance of checklists in aircraft operations.

A risk assessment is commonly conducted using risk matrixes, analysing the severity and the likelihood of an undesirable event (British Standards Institute, 2018). Despite extensive research, the author found no study or evidence on such a qualitative or quantitative assessment for checklists. However, the exemplary accidents have emphasised the potentially catastrophic results. The likelihood would be determined by using appropriate statistics, such as flight reports from crews experiencing this phenomenon, but no data or studies are publicly available for this particular risk. This is not surprising given that the recall of a memorised checklist reply almost always has no consequences due to the correct execution of the preceding workflow. Therefore, it is difficult for an individual to realise that the response correctly matched the current status but that this resulted from chance rather than a deliberate check. Consequently, pilots are often unaware of such instances and cannot report them.

Without data on the probability, the risk can be approached by analysing relevant barriers. The author created the following bow tie diagram³ visualising the risk of an inefficacious checklist execution before departure (cf. Figure 4 and for an enlarged format, see Appendix 1) without claiming to display all potential scenarios. It is a structured

³ A bow tie diagram is a structured depiction of triggers, barriers and potential consequences of a hazard. This tool is widely used in many high risk organisations to understand risks, identify and control suitable mitigations. However, it should be noted that there is no consistent definition or description of this concept as it developed from several analysis methods (de Ruijter and Guldenmund, 2016).

illustration of threats on the left (in blue), the undesirable top event of an inefficient checklist execution in the middle and possible consequences on the right (in red). Varicoloured bars between connecting lines represent three types of controls acting as barriers. Preventive controls are applied before the top event, and recovery controls are applied thereafter. The controls' efficacy could be diminished by escalation factors (yellow boxes), intended to be contained by escalation factor controls themselves. The colours of the controls represent the efficacy of mitigating a threat, either before the top event occurs or preventing a negative outcome thereafter. Three different classifications are used, with red representing the lowest potential to stop a causation and green representing the most efficacious controls.

Figure 4: Bow Tie Diagram for an Ineffective Checklist (own graphic)

Based on the recurring scenario of the accidents described before, the negative impact of specific human factors on checklist work is postulated in the top event to assess the implications for the remaining controls. This is necessary as the bow tie diagram does not allow the depiction of several prerequisites.

The threat of an inadequate aircraft configuration is exemplified hereafter. A first barrier is a correctly performed workflow according to standard operating procedures, such as setting the take-off flaps. A nonconformance by pilots would be an escalation factor. This is usually prevented by appropriate training (cf. Rantz et al., 2009). However, Hollnagel (2016) evaluates the efficiency of rules or procedures (“incorporeal barriers”) as low,

while other barriers could achieve medium or high efficiency. The European risk classification scheme (ERCS)⁴ in ‘Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/2034’ (2020) designates a barrier weight of three out of five for this category. The scheme rates barriers on a scale of one to five, with five being the most robust. Therefore, the bow tie diagram depicts this first barrier in orange. Additional escalation factors could be a stressed or interrupted crew. Potential controls such as being self-aware or maintaining a working environment without distractions are to be considered even less effective, only scoring an ERCS barrier weight of two and are therefore depicted in red. If working errors happen or a technical problem prevents a selected setting, pilot recognition through a cockpit scan or display indication is the following potential control. Considering these as either an incorporeal or a symbolic barrier, the effectiveness would be low or medium (Hollnagel, 2016). This aligns with an ERCS value of two for vigilance and situational awareness. During 60 cockpit observation flights, Dismukes and Berman (2010) found that crews detected half of the 62 system configuration errors. Four were categorised as aircraft configuration errors, with one remaining unnoticed. This also supports Hollnagel’s assessment.

An undetected inadequate aircraft configuration is a precondition for losing control over the hazard. In this case, the automatic checklist response does not coincide with the desired setting, and the top event, a failure to detect the incorrect state while performing the checklist, can be triggered. Conversely, correctly performed workflows will mostly conceal this issue and prevent consequences. An undetected incorrect condition is unsafe and potentially disastrous, but it is not yet an accident. The first recovery control is again a recognition by an individual with the same limitations as before. Just prior take-off, a configuration warning system (if installed) should detect the incorrect setting and alert the crew. The ERCS lists a barrier weight of three, focussing on the late stage of the event,

⁴ The ERCS is used to assess a risk after an occurrence and is therefore a retrospective means. The risk’s probability is obtained by consulting a barrier model which weighs the significance of various barriers (“barrier weight”) to stop an occurrence and considers their position in an event sequence. Nevertheless, the barrier weight can be interpreted without this context.

while Hollnagel (2016) assesses such a functional barrier with high efficiency. Based on this evaluation, a green depiction was chosen. However, as described in the accidents above, systems can fail. This needs to be mitigated through regular and effective maintenance. If the aircraft should take off with an incorrect configuration, e.g. without extended slats and flaps, the calculated performance cannot be achieved. The last control would be a successful recovery manoeuvre performed by the pilot flying to avoid a stall. Considering human factors like the startle effect and stress (Loukopoulos et al., 2009; Dekker, 2014), immediate and effective action cannot be taken for granted, as the aforementioned accidents show. Accordingly, the ERCS only weighs the barrier with one. Overall, if the checklist execution fails to detect a misconfiguration, the take-off configuration warning system is the only systematic barrier largely independent of human factors.

However, some procedures rely solely on correct flight crew actions without any subsequent warning systems. In many airlines, flight crews receive confirmation from the flight attendants that the cabin is secured for take-off or landing. The appropriate checklist typically includes this prerequisite for conducting the relevant flight phase. If this item is answered incorrectly, taking off or landing with an unsecured cabin can potentially result in serious injury to an occupant. A similar issue exists if erroneous performance calculations are inserted, but the crew confirms the correctness of the calculations and settings with a checklist. Some operators have implemented automatic crosschecks of aircraft parameters and the crew's calculations on the EFB. However, not all aircraft can accommodate such implementations, and not all operators choose to invest in them. This emphasises the significance of checklists as a barrier and raises questions about their efficacy and potential solutions.

4 Methodology

The following chapter describes the research strategies to answer the two research objectives. Descriptive research addresses RO1, determining how well pilots detect errors using a normal checklist. An experiment probes whether randomised checklist items affect the error detection rate compared to repetitively used normal checklists, answering RO2. The set-up of the conducted simulator observation is detailed, followed by a description of how the data was collected and analysed. Potential limitations end this chapter.

4.1 Research Strategy

The lack of academic research on the efficacy of normal checklists precluded the analysis of secondary data, such as a structured literature review, and required the acquisition of primary data. More specifically, determining how often a checklist is inefficacious in helping a crew to detect an inappropriate condition results in quantitative data. A pilot survey was one possibility, with the advantage of a large sample and easy set-up. On the other hand, surveys always depend on the truthfulness and memory of the respondents. Pilots may not want to admit they could recall checklist items or have already done so rather than deliberately checking them as expected. As described in Chapter 3, many participants may be unaware of instances where they replied automatically without consciously checking whether this represented the correct status. A survey was therefore ruled out.

Instead, the author elected to conduct an observational study of flight crew behaviour. The objective was to observe an atypical condition requiring a non-standard checklist response. As it is impractical to wait for and potentially dangerous to provoke such a condition during line flights, a full flight simulator observation was considered the most suitable means. Full flight simulators are authentic cockpit replicas with a display system mounted on a motion platform that can produce accelerations in line with the manoeuvres performed. These simulators are used for airline pilot training and offer a safe environment that can replicate realistic conditions. Flight crews are expected to demonstrate disciplined performance, which instructors assess.

Descriptive research was chosen to address RO1, measuring flight crews' error detection rate using a normal checklist. This non-experimental approach is often described as a suitable starting point for issues that have not been studied in detail and, consequently, lack scientific data (Grimes and Schulz, 2002). It allows to observe a specific situation without interfering (Siedlecki, 2020). The aim is to record the distribution of variables and, therefore, describe a status without the aspiration to explain what caused these results (Aggarwal and Ranganathan, 2019). Good and Scates (1954) thus used the term "status studies". This aligns with the first research objective. One disadvantage of descriptive studies is that they have a limited scope, in this case, only the participants of this observation. Consequently, the findings are not generalisable and descriptive studies can be difficult to be replicated precisely.

RO2 represents a further stage in the research process in that it seeks to analyse whether cognitive effects influence the execution of checklists. This is to be considered consequential research for the status study. An experiment was selected to test the following theory, for which Chapter 2 provided the theoretical background. If the repetition of recurring content favours implicit learning and triggers pattern recognition, repetitively performed checklists could be subject to these cognitive effects that impede controlled processing when checking items. An experiment allows for the testing of such causation by comparing the same conditions for two groups with only one altered causal agent (Coleman, 2019). The first requirement is fulfilled by subjecting all participants to an identical simulator scenario, in which an error should be detected with the appropriate checklist. The comparison is done with the crews' error detection rate representing the dependent variable. The checklist presentation will be the causal agent or independent variable (Coleman, 2019).

To probe the impact of cognitive processes on checklist performance, the author proposes that a random checklist item order can prevent implicit learning and pattern recognition. The arbitrary order may hinder implicit learning from the beginning by not repeating the same sequence. This cannot be reversed for pilots who have already learned the correlations, but the memory may fade over time. Relevant for this study, if a random checklist item presentation impedes pattern recognition and automaticity, it may prevent

the recall of memorised responses during checklist performance. This could be considered an intervention to facilitate controlled processing, as discussed in Chapter 2.2 (Shiffrin and Schneider, 1977; Barshi and Healy, 1993). The assumption is that the error detection rate and, consequently, the efficacy of the checklist can be enhanced. To demonstrate a correlation between the error detection rate and the checklist presentation, it is necessary to compare the results of a treatment group, which uses a randomised checklist, with those of a control group. The control group is not subjected to the treatment and uses a checklist presentation in the well-known order (Coleman, 2019). A significant difference in error detection rates between the two groups would indicate an effect of the randomised checklist presentation and, therefore, the impact of cognitive processes. The set-up of the study is depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Depiction of the Study Set-up (own graphic)

The expected results are essential for selecting the statistical test, which in turn influences the verbalization of the hypothesis. The observations for both groups are ultimately dichotomous: either the error is detected or not. As both groups were expected to detect the error predominantly, no standard distribution was to be expected. If the randomised checklist item order successfully prevents adverse cognitive effects and supports controlled processing, the error detection rate should be high, approaching 100%. These preconditions resulted in the selection of a Chi-Square Test of Independence, which is suitable to probe for a correlation between two variables but not the direction of the effect (McHugh, 2013).

Consequently, the hypothesis reads as follows:

A randomised checklist item sequence will prevent pattern recognition and, therefore, the recall of memorised responses, affecting the error detection rate.

H₀: There is no relationship between error detection rate and checklist item order.

H₁: There is a relationship between error detection rate and checklist item order.

To ascertain the required sample size for this experiment, an a priori power analysis was conducted using the tool G*Power (Faul et al., 2007). The parameters and results are shown in Appendix 2. The effect size and the significance level had to be estimated in the absence of comparable previous studies. As disciplined checklist execution can avert cognitive effects, the control group was also expected to detect the error predominantly. Therefore, the difference in error detection between the treatment and control groups was predicted to be less distinct. This resulted in the selection of an effect size of $w=.3$, which corresponds to a medium effect, according to Cohen (1988). Lacking evidence that could have indicated otherwise, the significance level was set at 5%, the most common standard in statistics (Coleman, 2019; Lakens et al., 2018). A minimum power of 80% was selected in accordance with widely accepted standards (Cohen, 1988). Two categories per variable equalled only one degree of freedom (Df). The calculation resulted in a minimum total sample size of 88 observations.

4.2 The Simulator Observation

The author developed a suitable simulator scenario, which was coordinated and subsequently introduced with the help of the training department of a European airline. This airline operates narrowbody jets connecting European cities. The scenario became part of the standardised recurrent simulator training programme for one of the fleets with approximately 30 aircraft. It consists of two full flight simulator sessions lasting four hours each. A commander and a first officer usually perform these missions under the supervision of an instructor who operates the simulator and provides feedback. The instructors were informed about how to conduct the observation through the programme's official description. Additionally, the author sent a letter requesting support (cf. Appendix

3) and contacted several instructors who performed the initial missions to explain the set-up. The programme lasted six months, from June to November 2022.

The simulator scenario was introduced during the last approach of the first session. Once the crew had configured the aircraft for landing, the instructor was supposed to fail the flap lever. This lever operates the slats and flaps system, hereinafter just referred to as flaps. This has no immediate effect and causes no noticeable indication, such as an aural or visual alert. After landing, the crew was supposed to taxi off the runway and perform the after-landing items, including flap retraction. As a result of the failure, the flap lever can be moved to the zero position, but no signal is sent to the flaps, which do not retract. The resulting discrepancy between the flap lever position and the actual flap setting does not cause any warnings or cautions. Subsequently, the crew was instructed to read the parking checklist (cf. excerpt of the simulator scenario description in Figure 6).

Time	Scenario	Setup	Instructor Notes
No. 4	2D RNP 34C - Landing		<p>👁️ Correct Configuration and adherence to approach profile</p> <p><i>When flaps are extended (flaps 20° indication):</i></p> <p>Select MALF INDEX > FLAPS & SLATS > FLAP CONTROL LEVER FAIL > ON [No. 2]</p> <p>⚠️ In case of Go-Around, the malfunction has to be cleared!</p>
No. 4	After Landing Items & Parking Checklist		<p>🗉 Instruct the crew to taxi off the runway to a stand. GRZ is a generic airport. Therefore advise to taxi off first possible to the right and park somewhere at the terminal building.</p> <p>⚠️ Standard After Landing items should be done while taxiing in.</p> <p><i>When reaching the stand:</i></p> <p>Hand over the prepared tablet with the displayed Parking Checklist to the crew.</p> <p>👁️ Do not give any further information and observe if the failed retraction of the flaps is recognised while reading the Parking Checklist.</p> <p>Additional instructor information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OA/C assists our colleague Moritz Bürger BMU in his master's degree with anonymized data. - The collected data compares a Parking Checklist in one SIM which is read in our every day's checklist sequence with a Parking Checklist in our other SIM device which is randomized via the app, so that the item sequence in the Parking Checklist changes every time. - The reason is obviously to check, whether the crew's attention is higher, if the item sequence is different to what they are used to (memory effects through constant repetition) - The recognition of the flap failure is not a part of the sim training / check and shall not be graded. - For the output of the master's examination it is very important not to reveal the purpose and set-up of this study situation. Therefore no feedback on the error should be provided to the crew. If the wrong flap setting is recognised at any point, please refer to this as an unintentional simulator glitch. <p><i>When the crew has finished reading the Parking Checklist:</i></p> <p>Fill out the short evaluation paper sheet and throw it in the provided box in the CLH locker (where you can also find the green QRH/QRC bags).</p>
01:10			
04:00	End of Session		

Figure 6: Scenario Description (own graphic)

The task-sharing requires the first officer (crew member 2) to read the items and the commander (crew member 1) to check and respond. This is discernible by the designator “1” at the end of each checklist item’s line, which stands for “crew member 1” (cf. Figure 7). Only the item “Headset” is designated with “B”, which stands for both, and requires a reply from both pilots. When checking the item “FLAPS”, the commander

should have recognised the discrepancy to the stipulated position zero. This European airline’s pilots normally use either a laminated paper checklist or a digital but equally static version on the EFB. However, to probe the impact of a randomised checklist version as part of this study, the instructor was supposed to hand a tablet with an interactive checklist application to the crew, as shown on the right of Figure 7. As this was the first time the crews used an interactive checklist, it could be argued that it may have caused distraction. However, any potential effect should have been limited to RO1, the overall error detection rate, and the first officer who used the checklist app to challenge the commander. The conditions for the comparison in RO2 were the same for all participants, as the checklists of both groups were equally presented.

Figure 7: Laminated Paper Checklist (left) and Checklist App (own graphic)

The checklist application (hereafter referred to as the “app”) was specifically programmed by the author for this study. It was modelled on the design and functionality of interactive checklist applications already available for use on airlines’ EFBs, as discussed in Chapter 2.5. The app’s unique feature was its capacity to randomise the order of checklist items. The app of the treatment group generated a unique item sequence, hypothetically preventing automatic behaviour and increasing the focus on each challenged item. The control group’s app appeared identical but displayed the conventional order of items well-known to the crew. This could have potentially triggered

pattern recognition and subconsciously recalling the standard response (“FLAPS zero”). The appropriate app loaded automatically after power-up without any user interaction required and readily displayed the required parking checklist (cf. Appendix 4 for details on the user experience). The format and font were similar to the original paper version, but the app was optimised for the dark simulator environment and allowed for interactive use of the tablet’s touchscreen. The colour of ticked off items changed from white to green. This could be undone by touching the item again if necessary. Upon selecting the “Checklist Complete” button, the app verified whether all items had been ticked off. If this was the case, the app confirmed completion. If any item remained incomplete, a warning message was displayed. A reset button cleared all ticked items, and the randomised checklist app additionally presented a new item order.

It is important to note that if such a randomised checklist presentation were to be implemented in daily operations, several consequences would have to be weighed against the potential benefit of preventing memorised expected replies. Aviation authorities and international standards recommend that checklists follow a sequence of urgency or a convenient flow (Federal Aviation Administration, 1995; Civil Aviation Authority, 2000; ICAO, 2018). Degani and Wiener (1991, p. 7) concur, listing ‘convenient sequences for motor movements and eye fixations along the cockpit panels’ as a checklist objective. This is not fulfilled anymore with a random sequence, and critical items could move to a posterior position. Furthermore, the less convenient execution for pilots compared to a well-known sequence and the position of the display device would have to be analysed regarding the acceptance of flight crews. Longer-term studies would have to be conducted to determine whether a cognitive link would develop between the challenged item and the standard response in the relevant situation, irrespective of the checklist sequence.

As cognitive effects can impact checklist execution unconsciously, it was imperative that crews were unbiased, not knowing the scenario in advance. Instructors and staff council members were advised on the importance of confidentiality as they were aware of the scenario. If a member of these two groups participated in a simulator mission, the observation was not to be recorded. Before the simulator mission, a briefing included solely information about a digital checklist app to be tested as part of a master’s degree

(cf. Appendix 5). As it is common for pilots to talk about the details of a simulator programme, instructors were supposed not to confront the crew with the failure or reveal the scenario afterwards. If the crew detected the error, the instructor was supposed to blame a simulator glitch. After the simulator mission, crew members received a questionnaire about the acceptance of a checklist app to rationalise the tablet use. These measures were supposed to prevent pilots from spreading the word about the failure scenario, prejudicing later participants.

4.3 Data Collection

The sample for RO1, the overall detection rate of the incorrect flap setting, consisted of all pilots of the European airline operating on the appropriate fleet except for instructors performing the mission as participants and staff council members, as both groups knew the scenario beforehand. This left approximately 150 flight crews (typically one captain and one first officer) scheduled for the simulator programme once. The restricted selection of pilots from a single company's fleet was inevitable due to the complexity of the set-up and represented a non-probability convenience sampling (Coleman, 2019). The results are thus only valid for this sample. However, the simulator observation could be repeated with any other pilot group.

This sample was subsequently divided into two groups for RO2, depending on the assignment to one of the two available simulators. The allocation is the training department's responsibility and typically results in an even distribution between the two simulators. Although this scheduling was deliberate on the part of the training department, it was unpredictable for the author and the study's participants. Therefore, this double-blind sampling can be considered as-if random within the previous non-probability convenience sampling (Crasnow, 2015; Coleman, 2019). Each tablet with its particular checklist version was dedicated to one of the simulators. All pilots in the first simulator (SIM 053) used the static version and represented the control group. All pilots in the second simulator (SIM 083) used the randomised checklist representing the treatment group. The tablets had been labelled with their appropriate simulator and were stored in different lockers, which include other necessary equipment dedicated to each simulator. Therefore, the tablets were easily accessible. The instructors had been advised not to

exchange the tablets. As both simulators, including their lockers, are located in different areas of the simulator centre, it is safe to assume this did not happen.

To obtain the flight crews' detection of the incorrect flap setting, the simulator instructors were supposed to observe and record the checklist execution regarding the response to the parking checklist's item "FLAPS". This represents a structured non-participant observation despite the instructor sitting directly behind the pilots, as there was no interaction with the crew during the checklist execution (Bell and Waters, 2017). Two forms in German were available for the recording of the observation. The sole distinction between the two was the indication of the designated simulator, which permitted the inference of which checklist presentation had been used. Each type of form was stored together with the respective tablet in the locker dedicated to the corresponding simulator. No personal data or dates were supposed to be recorded to protect anonymity. Figure 8 below shows an English translation of the form. Both original versions in German are available in Appendix 6.

Observation Sheet

SIM 053

Tick only one option and thereafter place it in the envelope in the locker please.

- Error already detected prior to checklist item FLAPS
- Error detected by CM1 at checklist item FLAPS
- Error not detected by CM1, but by CM2 at checklist item FLAPS
- Error was not detected or only distinctly after checklist item FLAPS

Figure 8: English Translation of an Instructor Observation Sheet (own graphic)

One of the following four options was supposed to be ticked off:

1. The error was detected before the checklist item “FLAPS”, e.g. due to monitoring of the flaps indication when the lever was moved.
2. The error was detected by the commander as intended.
3. The error was not detected by the commander but spotted by the first officer, despite no official obligation to check it.
4. The error was not detected or only distinctly after the checklist item “FLAPS”.

The instructor should have placed the observation sheet in an envelope in the aforementioned locker. The expectation was that 90% of the simulator missions would be recorded, allowing for some forgotten or deliberately omitted observations. In addition, it was necessary to account for the possibility that crews detected the error before reading the checklist, as this would have pre-empted an extemporaneous response. In the absence of previous studies or data, this probability was estimated using the barrier weights already used in Chapter 3. In the European risk classification scheme, checklists are best reflected as “situational awareness and action”, which is defined with a value of two by five according to ‘Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/2034’ (2020). Hollnagel (2016) assesses the efficiency of “incorporeal barriers”, including rules and procedures, as low (lowest of three ratings). Assuming that even the highest barrier effectiveness can hardly achieve 100% as this would imply infallibility, these two appraisals were converted to 30%. Together with the 10% allowance for not conducted observations, the total margin resulted in an expectation that usable records would be obtained for 63% of the scheduled simulator missions. This equated to 94 observations, which would still exceed the minimum sample size (88).

4.4 Data Analysis

The author had asked the contact person at the simulator centre to collect the observation sheets from the envelopes in the lockers and send digital scans on a monthly basis. This should have allowed for an analysis of changes in the detection rate over time. A significant increase in the detection rate could have indicated that the scenario had become known to the pilots. The originals were stored and made available to the author at the end of the study. Invalid returns were rejected. The remaining sheets were sorted

according to the simulator designation, and separate spreadsheets were created with the totals of the four options each (cf. Appendix 7 and 8). As explained in the previous chapter, the first option could be discarded for both research objectives. To analyse the overall flight crews' detection rate (RO1), another spreadsheet was employed to aggregate the total number of both the random (treatment group) and the static (control group) checklist presentations for each of the remaining three options. This was then used to calculate the percentages (cf. Appendix 9).

A fourth spreadsheet was used to compare the relevant figures for RO2 (cf. Appendix 10). In order to analyse the relationship between the checklist item sequence and the error detection rate, the results of the control and the treatment groups were supposed to be compared using the Chi-Square Test of Independence with the IBM SPSS Statistics software.

4.5 Limitations and Potential Hurdles

Although full flight simulators provide the most accurate replication of real-life situations, they are still an artificial environment, and study results may not generally apply to daily operations. However, it is expected that crews behave in the simulator as they would in an actual aircraft, particularly with regard to executing normal checklists according to established principles.

This study's sample does not represent all pilots as the behaviour, routines and discipline of the observed crews could differ from pilots of other airlines or flying different aircraft types. Additionally, several factors could have reduced the amount of data. First, the successful conduct depended on the cooperation and correct conduct of the instructors, as the author could not observe the simulator missions himself. The scenario was detailed in the instructors' simulator programme description, and they had been contacted separately via written communication requesting their assistance. The author additionally called several instructors who performed the first missions of the simulator training cycle to explain the study's set-up and purpose. It is noteworthy, however, that the training department regarded their participation as voluntary. It must also be acknowledged that the study constituted an additional effort which might not have been appreciated by

everyone. Observation errors or incorrect programming of the simulator seem very unlikely considering the background of the instructors, but they can also not be ruled out entirely. Second, uncertainty remained about how many crews would recognise the failure before reading the checklist, thereby dropping out of the evaluation. However, these effects were taken into account with a margin of more than 35 % on the minimum sample size.

The scenario required approval from the staff council to avoid any potential negative impact on the training, e.g. a frustrated crew if the error went undetected. Consequently, the observed scenario was placed at the very end of the simulator mission. Although crews are expected to remain focused until the end of their duty, as unexpected situations may arise at any time, crews may have started to relax and lose concentration, expecting that the simulator mission is over.

As already described, the study depended on unbiased behaviour, which required crews not to know the scenario. Several measures have been taken, as described in Chapter 4.2. Nevertheless, information leakage cannot be ruled out entirely although the author did not become aware of any. It is also possible that individual crew members performed the scenario more than once as an ad-hoc replacement for an unavailable colleague and already knew the error.

5 Findings of the Simulator Observation

Following the description of the research design and the simulator observation set-up, the data obtained will be analysed hereafter. The data will first be described in general terms, followed by the findings for each research objective, which will be contrasted with the literature review.

5.1 General Findings

The recurrent simulator programme, including the scenario relevant to this study, was conducted as planned from 1 June to 30 November 2022. This included the scenario description in the instructors' mission handout and a slide announcing the use of an interactive checklist in the briefing presentation. All objects required for the observations were available to the instructors. Scans of the completed observation sheets were sent on 4 August and after the end of the programme on 10 December. The originals were collected together with all other equipment on 3 January 2023. The tablets were still in the same good working condition as when they had been delivered.

The study yielded 48 observation sheets, 21 from the control group with the static checklist and 27 from the treatment group with the randomised checklist. One sheet of the control group was rejected as no option had been marked. The remaining papers clearly indicated the selected choice and contained no other markings, notes or similar. This indicates that the simulator instructors who recorded their observation understood the task. However, the number of returned observations corresponds to only approximately one third of the eligible simulator missions.

The control group's observations comprised seven error detections before the checklist was read (Option 1), nine discoveries by the commander when the corresponding item was challenged (Option 2), none by the first officer in case the commander did not spot the misconfiguration (Option 3), and four times the error was not detected at all (Option 4). The treatment group's distribution consisted of nine times Option 1, eleven times Option 2, three times Option 3 and four times Option 4 (cf. Figure 9).

Figure 9: Data Analysis of Observation Sheets (own graphic)

As indicated in Figure 10, the sum of all 47 valid observations resulted in 16 detections of the incorrect flap setting even before the checklist was read (34%). This matches the ERCS barrier weight for ‘situational awareness and action’ in ‘Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/2034’ (2020, p. 7) quite well, defined as two from five. While this is a good sign for the attentiveness of crew members, no information is available about the cause of these detections, and it cannot be assumed that similar results could be expected in any other failure situation as the circumstances or habits can be completely different.

Figure 10: Total Error Detection (own graphic)

The first Option has to be taken out of consideration for the scope of this study as it pre-empted the checklist's function. This reduces the number of valid observations to analyse the two research objectives to 31.

During the six-month simulator training cycle, no problems with the tablets or the software were reported, generally suggesting the suitability of the set-up. There was no indication that the scenario had become known to the pilots or that using an interactive checklist app in the simulator had become a topic of conversation. However, it was impossible to analyse any trends because the observation sheets were only sent once during the simulator programme, on 4 August. By then, ten observations had been conducted in the control group and 17 in the treatment group. Apart from implementing the intended periodic extraction, another option would have been to record the calendar week on the observation sheets. This could have also made it possible to evaluate trends in detection rates while still maintaining confidentiality.

5.2 Simulator Observation Findings Answering RO1

The measurement of flight crews' detection rate of the technical error using any of the two normal checklists, the static or the randomised version, allowed for two alternatives. First, a strict interpretation of the envisaged task-sharing providing that only the commander checks and responds to the challenged item "FLAPS", as explained in Chapter 4.2. In this case, missing the incorrect configuration by the captain but the subsequent recognition through the first officer (Option 3) counts as a non-detection. With this first approach, 20 commanders detected the incorrect flap setting, equalling 64% (cf. Figure 11). The second possibility is to consider crew performance by including error detections of the first officer even though the colleague replied incorrectly. This is reasonable as commercial airline operations rely on two pilots to improve resilience, support each other and detect errors which would otherwise remain unnoticed (ICAO, 1998; Bailey et al., 2017). Therefore, it is good practice for first officers to check the items themselves and provide a backup. This proved successful three times in the study (10%) and increased the combined error detection rate of the crew to 74%.

Figure 11: Error Detection Rate with Checklist (own graphic)

Conversely, at least 26% of the crews (8) and 36% of the individual commanders (11) did not detect the incorrect indication. This is a substantial amount considering the criticality of checklists in detecting hazardous conditions, as demonstrated in the Literature Review and the risk assessment. These findings align with the cockpit observation flights described by Degani and Wiener (1993) as well as Dismukes and Berman (2010). However, no values are directly comparable due to the different preconditions. Likewise, it is not possible to contrast figures whether crew members of this study skipped the checklist, replied without looking or misinterpreted the indication as this was not recorded. The instructors might have been able to provide such information, but an accurate analysis would have required special equipment to record eye-tracking. Although the interactive checklist presentation differed from the laminated paper checklist usually used, the working principle remained the same and should not have affected the error detection. It is reasonable to posit that both crew members wanted to perform well under the observation of an instructor and, consequently, did not deliberately violate operating procedures. Therefore, it is likely that all participants performed the checklist, and that the incorrect reply coincided with the well-known desired response. Any other answer, or none at all, would have triggered a reaction from the second crew member. In any case, these data cannot explain what caused the crew members to reply incorrectly and whether cognitive processes such as automaticity or pattern recognition had any effect.

The fact that one in four crews failed to detect an error despite performing the relevant checklist raises concerns about the envisaged efficacy of checklists in aircraft operations. The literature did not provide publicly available values or qualitative descriptions that could serve as a benchmark. The aviation industry has defined different target levels of safety for particular types of commercial operations and specific flight phases. The most commonly cited values range from 10^{-7} to 10^{-8} events per flight hour (Lin et al., 2009). A likelihood of 10^{-9} is often defined for the failure of individual system components, assuming a 10% contribution to a catastrophic accident, which should occur less than once per one million flights (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2018). These values demonstrate the aviation system's commitment to accident prevention. Even though the checklist is just one of several available barriers (cf. the bow tie diagram in Chapter 3), a failure rate of 25% (equivalent to more than 10^{-2}) is deemed unacceptable. To achieve a level within the range of the aforementioned values, not a single crew would have been allowed to miss the incorrect setting in this observation. This would have applied even if the expected sample size had been reached.

To summarise the findings for RO1, the flight crews' detection rate of the technical error introduced in the simulator observation was far below any standard which should be expected in aviation. The normal cockpit checklists used in this scenario were not efficacious in helping the crews to reliably detect the incorrect condition of the checklist item "FLAPS". However, it should be reiterated that the error detection rate obtained in this study cannot be taken as a generic value for all flight crews. Further studies are required to validate this observation.

5.3 Simulator Observation Findings Answering RO2

To probe the relationship between checklist item order and error detection rate, the observations of the control and treatment groups are compared. The 16 detections of the incorrect flap setting before the checklist was read (34%) slightly exceeded the expected amount of 30% (cf. Chapter 4.3). After rejecting this first option for both groups, only 13 observations remained for the control group and 18 for the treatment group. These 31 data sets represented just 20% of the eligible sample. This undercut the minimum sample size of 88 calculated in the a priori power analysis by far (65%), rendering any analysis with

the Chi-Square Test for Independence insignificant. The hypothesis of a relationship between error detection rate and checklist item order could not be confirmed accordingly. Extrapolating the 34% exclusion rate of errors detected before reading the checklist (Option 1) results in a minimum sample of 134. Therefore, 90% of the simulator missions should have been observed instead of the 31% valid returns achieved. There is no representative explanation for this shortfall, but some instructors told the author that they considered the observation too much extra work. This seems surprising given the arrangements that had been made (cf. Appendix 3 and 4). On the other hand, the author experienced that not all instructors in this fleet strictly follow the simulator programmes as published, e.g. do not use the assigned briefing presentation or change parts of the mission. This may explain why so many instructors chose not to carry out the observations as described. Therefore, a reiteration of this study would require much better observer compliance or a larger sample.

Although no scientific findings can be drawn from the data, some remarks should be made. The detection rate of only the treatment group's commanders (Option 2) was 61%, considering subsequent error recognitions of the treatment group's first officers as a non-detection (cf. Figure 12). This is very low compared to the expectation that a randomised checklist item order would support controlled processing and therefore a focus on the displayed indication, resulting in a near-perfect error recognition. Equal to RO1, it is very likely that all participants performed the randomised checklist, and the incorrect reply coincided with the well-known desired response for the reasons provided in the previous chapter. As the appropriate display should have indicated a different setting, the answer must have been recalled from memory. That would imply the possibility that a particular memorised response was not triggered by a pattern consisting of several successive checklist items but solely by the challenged item itself. However, this would require an unconscious link between the requested item, the current situation (i.e. the appropriate checklist) and the common reply appropriate to that situation, as there is usually more than one correct answer to a challenged item. In the case of the item "FLAPS" used in the study, the pilot is used to the options "zero" after landing, "eight" or "twenty" for take-off and "45" for landing. Such a connection contradicts the pattern recognition

theory outlined in the Literature Review, but cannot be ruled out and should therefore be tested in future studies.

Figure 12: Comparison of Error Detection Rates with Checklist (own graphic)

Another noteworthy point is the first officers' error detection, which occurred exclusively in the treatment group using the randomised order of checklist items. Therefore, if it is included in the crew's error detection rate, only the treatment group's performance rises to 78%, while the control group's remains unchanged. This seems surprising as any distracting influence of the randomisation should have particularly affected the first officer who read the checklist. The impact of the interactive presentation, e.g. the possibility to tick completed items, was the same for both groups. However, due to the small sample size, this must be considered an insignificant effect, and therefore, no conclusions should be drawn.

To summarise the findings for RO2, the hypothesis of a relationship between error detection rate and checklist item order could not be tested due to insufficient sample size. Consequently, it was impossible to investigate the effect of human cognitive processes on checklist execution, i.e. pattern recognition and the subsequent recall of memorised responses.

6 Conclusion

This project aimed to assess the efficacy of normal cockpit checklists in detecting undesired conditions considering human cognitive processes. The literature review demonstrated the critical role of these checklists in aircraft operations, ensuring that all necessary tasks have been completed as prescribed. A static presentation without electronic closed-loop functionality is still the predominant application on many aircraft types. Pilots must repetitively check and accurately interpret all items that have often been set during a previous workflow. Cognitive research suggests that this can have a negative impact on the performance of checklists, and corresponding accidents seem to support this.

Therefore, the first research objective measured the flight crews' detection rate of a technical error introduced in a simulator observation. Approximately one in four crews did not detect the incorrect setting despite checking the appropriate item. This anomaly has already been described in previous studies, however without specifically measuring a detection rate. This study's result is below any level of safety that should be expected in aviation. Therefore, the normal cockpit checklists were not efficacious in helping the crews to reliably detect the incorrect condition in this observation.

The second research objective was supposed to probe the impact of cognitive processes by comparing the error detection rate of a treatment group using a randomised checklist with a control group using a well-known static normal checklist. The experiment's hypothesis stated that a randomised sequence of checklist items would prevent pattern recognition and, consequently, the recall of memorised responses. However, the effect of human cognitive processes on checklist execution could not be tested due to insufficient observations, resulting in a sample size that was too small for a significant analysis. Therefore, the study could not provide any results for research objective two.

Overall, this study suggests that normal cockpit checklists may not be efficacious enough in detecting incorrect conditions to a level of safety expected in commercial aviation. This issue is particularly pertinent when operators are subject to external stressors such as time

pressure or distraction, which can result in the reversion to known patterns. Correctly performed workflows mostly conceal this problem and prevent consequences or any obvious opportunity to recognise replies that do not originate from controlled processing. The study could not determine the effects of specific cognitive processes on checklist execution. However, this would be essential to systematically review the status of normal cockpit checklists and potentially optimise their use. Pilots should be made aware of the inherent danger of subconsciously replying from memory, e.g. during crew resource management training or check flights. Suitable scenarios highlighting the importance of slow and deliberate checklist execution could also be integrated into simulator training.

7 Suggestions for Further Research

As the first research objective found an alarming error detection rate and no causal link between cognitive effects on checklist use and the error detection rate could be determined, this study recommends further research on this particular issue with flight crews, reiterating the recommendation of Barshi and Healy (1993).

Therefore, a replication of the observation described in this paper is recommended with minor modifications to reduce some limitations. Most importantly, a higher commitment from the observers would be required to obtain a sufficient sample size. It is also recommended to select a larger group of pilots, e.g. by conducting the experiment on the single-aisle fleet of a major airline with 50 or more aircraft. This airline would preferably already be using an interactive checklist application. Pilots would be used to such a tool, and adding the randomised checklist version to the available hardware would be easier. The (technical) error should be placed in the middle of the simulator mission to reduce the risk of participants losing concentration towards the end. Finally, recording the calendar week on the observation sheets or a weekly collection would be beneficial. This would allow to draw inferences about the trend of the error detection rate and possibly an analysis if the scenario has become known to pilots.

A different but more artificial approach is using eye-tracking devices during checklist performance. This has already been suggested by Dismukes and Berman (2010) and would allow tracking the pilot's focus during the checklist, as well as the duration of each glance. Such devices should be used for both crew members to also observe, whether first officers are verifying items that they are not legally required to check according to operating procedures. In addition, the impact of the location of interactive checklists could be scrutinised, e.g. when this solution is integrated into an EFB mounted out of sight of the items being checked. However, it is important to note that such an obviously scientific set-up would make it more challenging to observe unaffected pilot behaviour, which is crucial for detecting subconscious processes.

Organisations should assess the remaining barriers after the last appropriate checklist to determine the risks associated with the recall of incorrect checklist replies. The accidents

described in Chapter 2.4 have highlighted the potential consequences if subsequent barriers also fail. Where critical items have no additional barriers, the severity of an incident should be carefully assessed. Examples include the setting of performance parameters or cabin status reports.

Human factor analysis should also focus on several aspects of normal checklist performance. Mindfulness plays an important role, as pilots are particularly vulnerable to automatic behaviours when under stress or distracted. However, maintaining controlled processing requires self-awareness of one's state of mind. It should be assessed whether crew members can reliably control their work discipline and judge possible consequences of influences such as workload, time pressure, fatigue, tiredness, boredom or simply repetitive tasks. This goes hand in hand with the role of training, which could improve checklist discipline, as suggested by some of the aforementioned studies (Rantz et al., 2009; Rantz and van Houton, 2011). However, it is not determined how long such effects last.

Finally, there is the influence of another crew member on checklist performance, which is becoming increasingly important with the growth of single-pilot commercial operations, such as piloted urban air mobility vehicles, commonly referred to as “air taxis” (Garrow et al., 2021), or single-pilot cockpit concepts (Harris, 2023). In the absence of a pilot monitoring, it is necessary to assess whether an individual works more disciplined, knowing that no one else can detect an error, or whether the opposite is true, e.g. due to increased complacency.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Enlarged Format of the Bow Tie Diagram for an Ineffective Checklist (own graphic)

Appendix 2: G*Power a Priori Power Analysis (own graphic)

Appendix 3: English Translation of the Information Letter to the Instructors

Dear colleagues,

As you may have read in the simulator programme, the training department will support my thesis in Air Safety Management during the upcoming recurrent programme. The scenario at the end of the LOFT mission is crucial for me to analyse so-called primary data, i.e. scientific findings that do not yet exist. Your support would be greatly appreciated.

I understand that this requires extra effort from you, although I have tried to minimise it as much as possible:

- The tablet assigned to the appropriate simulator should be in the green bag along with its charger (please do not swap tablets under any circumstances!)
- The observation sheets and the survey for the debriefing are also stored in the lockers
- It would be appreciated if the tablet could be charged during the briefing of each morning mission and then taken into the simulator in the bag
- It is recommended that the tablet is not switched on until the last approach of the LOFT to ensure sufficient battery power
- The app takes a maximum of one minute to boot up and starts automatically
- Please inform the crews that the app is interactive. All items can be ticked off and at the end, they can click on “Checklist completed”
- Please do not add any extra notes on the observation sheets (one per crew) and place them in the corresponding envelope in the locker
- The observation sheets are crucial for me. If the crews choose not to complete the survey, it is no issue

Even if you do not value the study or do not wish to support me, please do not disclose any information about the scenario. Once the crews were to find out, the entire study would become invalid.

Many thanks for your support! I really appreciate it.

Moritz

Appendix 4: Tablet and Checklist Apps User Experience

The simulator observation involved using two different tablet models, each with its individual cover, as depicted in Figure 13. The first tablet hosting the static checklist app (SIM 053) was a ten-inch CAPTIVA Pad 10.1 with Windows 10 operating system and a blue cover weighing 870g. The second tablet hosting the randomised checklist app (SIM 083) was an 11.6-inch ASUS Vivo Tab TF810C with Windows 8.1 operating system and a green cover weighing 920g. Both tablets were labelled with the appropriate simulator in which they were supposed to be used and instructions in German on how to use them. The instructions included details on the power switch and power supply connection, the fact that the app would start automatically, and how long this would take.

Figure 13: Both Tablets Hosting the Individual Checklist Apps (own graphic)

Upon pressing the power switch, the relevant app loaded automatically. The operating system booted and initiated the login procedure, after which the checklist app launched without user intervention. The checklist app had been programmed by the author and was executed in full-screen mode running in the Microsoft Edge browser (cf. Figure 14). The parking checklist was the only checklist available. Each item could be ticked off, changing the colour from white to green. This was reversible by pressing the item again.

Figure 14: Static Item Sequence on the Left and Randomised Item Sequence on the Right (own graphic)

Once all items had been ticked off, the “Checklist Complete” button turned from grey to blue. Pressing the button confirmed the completion of the checklist. If the button was pressed while items remained unchecked, a warning message appeared as depicted on the right side of Figure 15. A reset button was available to clear all checked items. A new item order was then created on the randomised checklist app only.

Figure 15: Possible Outcomes of the “Checklist Complete” Button (own graphic)

Both devices and their chargers were stored in dedicated lockers that also contained additional equipment required for the simulators, such as manuals and other checklists. The instructor responsible for the first mission of the day collects this equipment and brings it to the simulator, where it can remain as long as crews of this operator are scheduled. To conduct the simulator observation, the tablet and one observation sheet had to be taken as well. The tablet's battery was intended to be recharged during the briefing to ensure sufficient power. However, it could also be charged at the instructor's seat in the simulator. Following the insertion of the technical error at the end of the simulator mission, the instructor should have switched on the tablet so that the checklist app would be available for the crew after taxi-in. After observing whether the crew detected the incorrect condition, one option should have been marked on the observation sheet, which then should have been returned to the appropriate locker. During the debriefing, a questionnaire should have been given to the crew to justify using the checklist app.

Appendix 5: Slide presented in the Simulator Briefing (own graphic)

Master Thesis

Trial of Checklist App as Part of Master Thesis

- OA-T supports the master thesis of one of our colleagues
- At the end of the LOFT mission, you will be asked to perform a PARKING checklist using an app on a dedicated tablet
- Please work this checklist as thoroughly as usual
- During the debriefing, please evaluate 10 questions of an anonymous questionnaire about your experiences and opinion relating to such a potential app

Appendix 6: Original Instructor Observation Sheets in German (own graphic)

Beobachtungsauswertung

SIM 053

Nur eine Option ankreuzen und bitte anschließend in den Umschlag im Schließschrank legen.

- Fehler bereits vor Checklist-Item FLAPS entdeckt
- Fehler von CM1 bei Checklist-Item FLAPS entdeckt
- Fehler nicht von CM1, aber von CM2 bei Checklist-Item FLAPS entdeckt
- Fehler wurde nicht bemerkt oder erst deutlich nach Checklist-Item FLAPS

Beobachtungsauswertung

SIM 083

Nur eine Option ankreuzen und bitte anschließend in den Umschlag im Schließschrank legen.

- Fehler bereits vor Checklist-Item FLAPS entdeckt
- Fehler von CM1 bei Checklist-Item FLAPS entdeckt
- Fehler nicht von CM1, aber von CM2 bei Checklist-Item FLAPS entdeckt
- Fehler wurde nicht bemerkt oder erst deutlich nach Checklist-Item FLAPS

Appendix 7: Spreadsheet SIM 053 Static Checklist

STATIC CHECKLIST

	Total	Percentage	
Option 1	7	35,0%	Error already detected before checklist item FLAPS
Option 2	9	45,0%	Error detected by CM1 at checklist item FLAPS
Option 3	0	0,0%	Error not detected by CM1, but by CM2 at checklist item FLAPS
Option 4	4	20,0%	Error was not detected or only distinctly after checklist item FLAPS
Invalid	1		Invalid
Total	20	100,0%	Without Invalid
Error	detected	undetected	
	69,2%	30,8%	with Checklist solely by CM1 (disregards Option 1)
	69,2%	30,8%	with Checklist by CM1 or CM2 (disregards Option 1)

Appendix 8: Spreadsheet SIM 083 Random Checklist

RANDOM CHECKLIST

	Total	Percentage	
Option 1	9	33,3%	Error already detected before checklist item FLAPS
Option 2	11	40,7%	Error detected by CM1 at checklist item FLAPS
Option 3	3	11,1%	Error not detected by CM1, but by CM2 at checklist item FLAPS
Option 4	4	14,8%	Error was not detected or only distinctly after checklist item FLAPS
Invalid	0		Invalid
Total	27	100,0%	Without Invalid
Error	detected	undetected	
	61,1%	38,9%	with Checklist solely by CM1 (disregards Option 1)
	77,8%	22,2%	with Checklist by CM1 or CM2 (disregards Option 1)

Appendix 9: Spreadsheet RO1 Error Detection

RO1 ERROR DETECTION

	Total	Percentage	
Option 1	16	34,0%	Error already detected before checklist item FLAPS
Option 2	20	42,6%	Error detected by CM1 at checklist item FLAPS
Option 3	3	6,4%	Error not detected by CM1, but by CM2 at checklist item FLAPS
Option 4	8	17,0%	Error was not detected or only distinctly after checklist item FLAPS
Total	47		

RO1 ERROR DETECTION RATE WITH CHECKLIST

	Total	Percentage	
Option 1	16		Error already detected before checklist item FLAPS
Option 2	20	64,5%	Error detected by CM1 at checklist item FLAPS
Option 3	3	9,7%	Error not detected by CM1, but by CM2 at checklist item FLAPS
Option 4	8	25,8%	Error was not detected or only distinctly after checklist item FLAPS
Total	31		
Opt. 2	20	64,5%	Error detected with Checklist solely by CM1 (disregards Option 1)
Opt. 2+3	23	74,2%	Error detected with Checklist by CM1 or CM2 (disregards Option 1)

Appendix 10: Spreadsheet RO2 Comparison

RO2 COMPARISON

	SIM 053 STATIC		SIM 083 RANDOM		
Option 1	7	35,0%	9	33,3%	Error already detected before checklist item FLAPS
Option 2	9	45,0%	11	40,7%	Error detected by CM1 at checklist item FLAPS
Option 3	0	0,0%	3	11,1%	Error not detected by CM1, but by CM2 at checklist item FLAPS
Option 4	4	20,0%	4	14,8%	Error was not detected or only distinctly after checklist item FLAPS
Total	20		27		
Opt. 2	9	69,2%	11	61,1%	Error detected with Checklist by CM1 (disregards Option 1)
Opt. 2+3	9	69,2%	14	77,8%	Error detected with Checklist by CM1 or CM2 (disregards Option 1)
Total	13		18		Total Options disregarding Option 1